

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Substituted Mandelic Acids by Sodium N-chlorobenzenesulphonamide

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Manuscript received 5 May 1981, revised 25 November 1981, accepted 7 January 1982

The oxidation of mandelic acid and nine monosubstituted mandelic acids by sodium N-chlorobenzenesulphonamide has been studied in aqueous acetic acid and perchloric acid. The reaction is of first order with respect to the concentrations of the oxidant, the hydroxy acid and hydrogen ions. The primary kinetic isotope effect (k_H/k_D) is 5.11 ± 0.06 at 303 K. The solvent isotope effect $[k(H_2O)/k(D_2O)]$ is 0.406 at 303 K. The reaction exhibits a reaction constant $\rho^* = -2.13$ at 303 K. $PhSO_2NHCl$ has been postulated as the active oxidising species. The rates were determined at four temperatures and the activation parameters were evaluated. A mechanism involving transfer of a hydride ion to the oxidant has been suggested.

CHLORAMINE-T (CAT) and N-bromosuccinimide (NBS) are well known organic positive halogen compounds and several reports have appeared on the mechanism of their reactions^{1,2}. Another compound of this category is sodium N-chlorobenzenesulphonamide (chloramine-B or CAB). Not much information is available on the mechanism of oxidation by CAB excepting that of alcohols³. It is known that reactions of NBS with alcohols and hydroxy acids follow different mechanisms^{3,4}. This prompted us to undertake this investigation.

Results and Discussion

The rate laws and other experimental data were obtained for all the substituted mandelic acids. Since results are similar, only those of mandelic acids are described.

Product analysis: Oxidation of mandelic acid by CAB in the presence of $HClO_4$ results in the formation of phenylglyoxylic acid and benzenesulphonamide. Product analysis and stoichiometry determinations indicated the following overall reaction:

Rate laws: The reaction is of total third order, being first order with respect to CAB, mandelic acid and hydrogen ions. The pseudo-first-order rate constants for varying concentration of one component keeping the concentrations of other components constant are presented in Table 1. When acid strength was varied, ionic strength was kept constant at 1.0 M using sodium perchlorate.

Influence of radical traps: The reaction is not affected by added radical scavengers like allyl acetate as allyl acetate, up to 0.02 M, did not affect the oxidation rate. The oxidation of mandelic acid in an atmosphere of nitrogen failed to induce polymerisation of acrylonitrile.

Isotope effects: Experiments were conducted with α -deuteriomandelic acid $[PhCD(OH)COOH]$

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE OXIDATION OF MANDELIC ACID BY CAB AT 303 K

[MA] M	[CAB] M	[H ⁺] M	10 ⁶ k ₁ sec ⁻¹
0.05	0.005	0.5	3.08
0.10	0.005	0.5	6.00
0.20	0.005	0.5	12.0
0.40	0.005	0.5	23.8
0.50	0.005	0.5	31.0
0.20	0.010	0.5	11.9
0.20	0.020	0.5	12.3
0.20	0.080	0.5	12.2
0.10	0.005	0.1	1.25
0.10	0.005	0.2	2.60
0.10	0.005	0.3	3.80
0.10	0.005	0.4	5.18

to ascertain the importance of cleavage of C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The primary kinetic isotope effect, k_H/k_D , has a value of 5.11 ± 0.06 at 303 K (Table 2).

TABLE 2—KINETIC ISOTOPE EFFECT IN THE OXIDATION OF MANDELIC ACID

[CAB]=0.005 M; [H⁺]=0.5 M; Temp.=303 K

[MA] M	Type	10 ⁶ k ₁ sec ⁻¹	
0.05	H	3.03	
0.10	H	6.00	$10^6 k_H = 12.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ l}^2 \text{ mole}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$
0.20	H	11.9	
0.10	D	1.18	
0.20	D	2.35	$10^6 k_D = 2.35 \pm 0.02 \text{ l}^2 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$
0.30	D	3.50	

$$k_H/k_D = 5.11 \pm 0.06$$

The oxidation of mandelic acid was studied in 95% deuterium oxide. The rate constants for the oxidation in H_2O and D_2O at 303 K are $10^6 k = 4.67$ and $11.5 \text{ l}^2 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively. The

solvent isotope effect, $k(\text{H}_2\text{O})/k(\text{D}_2\text{O})=0.406$. In this set of experiments acetic acid was not added to the solvent.

Dependence on solvent composition : The effect of variation of solvent composition on the oxidation rate has been studied in binary mixture of acetic acid and water. The reaction rate increases slightly with increasing proportion of acetic acid in the solvent (Table 3).

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF THE REACTION RATE ON SOLVENT COMPOSITION

[MA]=0.10, Percentage of acetic acid (v/v) $10^4 k_1$, sec ⁻¹	[CAB]=0.005 M	[H ⁺]=0.5	Temp.=303 K
	0	20	35
	2.84	3.71	4.80
		50	60
			7.75

Addition of benzenesulphonamide (up to 0.05 M) did not affect the reaction rate.

Influence of substituents : The effects of *m*- and *p*-substituents in the mandelic acid molecule on the oxidation rate have been studied with nine different mono-substituted compounds. The rates were obtained at different temperatures between 303–318 K and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 4). The average error limits in the values of $\Delta H^\ddagger$, $\Delta S^\ddagger$ and $\Delta G^\ddagger$ (at 303 K) are ± 4 kJ mol⁻¹, ± 6 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹ and ± 5 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively.

TABLE 4—RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF SUBSTITUTED MANDELIC ACIDS BY CAB

Substituent	$10^4 k_1$ mol ⁻² sec ⁻¹				$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹
	303	308	313	318 K			
H	120	173	250	362	61.4	128	100
<i>p</i> -F	85.2	125	184	274	64.8	120	101
<i>p</i> -Cl	69.2	103	155	234	66.1	117	101
<i>p</i> -Br	58.8	87.4	133	202	67.4	113	102
<i>p</i> -Et	501	660	864	1140	44.0	165	94.0
<i>p</i> -Pr ^t	468	614	808	1070	44.7	164	94.4
<i>p</i> -OMe	5490	6810	6940	7820	21.6	228	90.7
<i>m</i> -Cl	18.6	28.6	47.3	77.7	78.7	86.5	105
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	4.47	7.90	14.4	25.8	96.8	40.2	108
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	2.68	4.76	9.02	16.7	102	27.4	110

Not much information is available about the equilibria present in acidified CAB solution, though the same have been reported in detail for CAT in acid solution⁵⁻⁸. Assuming that CAB behaves like CAT, the following equilibria are possible in acidified CAB solution (where R = PhSO₂):

The probable oxidising species are RNHCl, RNCl₂ and HOCl. Soper⁸ has shown that the concentration of HOCl in acidified CAT is very small and is independent of CAT concentration.

The predominant species is TsNHCl and the concentration of TsNCl₂ is proportional to that of TsNHCl. Thus one can conclude that the relative amounts of the probable oxidising species will not change with CAB concentration and the reaction will show first order dependence on CAB in spite of the variety of species present. However, dichloramine-B (RNCl₂) can be ruled out as the reactive species in view of the strict first order dependence on CAB. In the reaction of related sodium *N*-bromobenzenesulphonamide the effect of HOBr was observed as an initial deviation in the kinetic curve, before its contribution was stifled by the product benzenesulphonamide⁹. Initially added benzenesulphonamide eliminated this deviation. In the present investigation no deviation was observed in the kinetic curve. Thus, any role of HOCl even in the initial stages of the reaction is unlikely. Further, no effect of benzenesulphonamide on the reaction rate precludes both HOCl and RNCl₂ as the oxidising species. This leaves RNHCl or PhSO₂NHCl as the most probable oxidising species. This supports the conclusion of Ruff and Kucsman¹⁰ that in the oxidation of organic sulphides by CAT in strongly acidic solvents, TsNHCl alone is the reactive species.

The increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solution decreases the polarity of the solvent and favours reactions in which uncharged molecules are formed from ion¹¹. Therefore, the equilibrium (2) is favoured by solvent with increasing amounts of acetic acid which may explain the observed rate enhancement.

The large primary kinetic isotope effect confirms that the rate-determining step involves cleavage of C-H bond from the carbon bearing the functional groups.

The activation enthalpies and entropies of the ten compounds are linearly related ($r=0.9990$). The correlation was tested and found genuine by applying Exner's criterion¹². The isokinetic temperature computed from the plot is 407 K. Current views do not attach much physical significance to isokinetic temperature¹³, though a linear correlation is usually a necessary condition for the validity of linear free energy relationships.

An insight into the transition state of the oxidation may be obtained from the analysis of the effect of substituents on the reaction rate. The introduction of electron-withdrawing groups decreases the rate of oxidation while electron-donating groups have reverse effect. The oxidation rates correlate very well with Brown's σ^+ values¹⁴ with large negative reaction constants. The values of reaction constant, $\rho^\ddagger$, are -2.13 ($r=0.9935$), -2.00 ($r=0.9933$), -1.85 ($r=0.9934$) and -1.71 ($r=0.9933$) at 303 K, 308 K, 313 K and 318 K, respectively. The negative values of $\rho^\ddagger$ indicate an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state.

A hydrogen abstraction mechanism may be discounted in view of the nil effect of radical

scavengers and the magnitude of the reaction constant. In most reactions involving hydrogen abstraction, the reaction constants have small magnitudes¹⁴. The large negative reaction constant together with the substantial deuterium isotope effect indicate a considerable carbonium ion character in the transition state. The above results suggest a hydride ion transfer in the rate-determining step.

Natarajan and Thiagarajan¹⁵ suggested formation of a hypochlorite ester as the rate-determining step in the oxidation of 2-propanol by CAT in acid solution. However, the observed solvent isotope effect does not indicate any involvement of the hydroxyl either in the rate-determining step or in the pre-equilibria. Correlation with σ^+ values also suggests an intermolecular hydride ion transfer. The observed kinetic isotope effect is also rather large for the non-linear transition state implied in the ester mechanism. The following mechanism may then be proposed.

The following rate equation may be derived for the above mechanism :

$$-d[\text{PhSO}_2\text{NCl}^-]/dt = k_2[\text{PhSO}_2\text{NHCl}][\text{MA}] \quad (10)$$

$$= k_2 K [\text{PhSO}_2\text{NCl}^-] [\text{H}_2\text{O}^+][\text{MA}] \quad (11)$$

where MA = mandelic acid

Eq. (11) requires that the reaction should exhibit a first order dependence on CAB, the hydroxy acid and hydrogen ions. This agrees with the experimentally derived rate laws.

Experimental

Materials : The preparations and specification of the mandelic acids have been described earlier¹⁶. The isotopic purity of α -deuteriomandelic acid, as ascertained by its nmr spectrum was $92 \pm 5\%$. Chloramine-B was prepared by chlorination of an alkaline solution of benzenesulphonamide¹⁷. The crude product was recrystallised from hot water. The purity was checked by determining the amount of active chlorine iodometrically. Acetic acid was purified by usual methods¹⁸. Perchloric acid was used as a source of hydrogen ions.

Product analysis and stoichiometry : Mandelic acid (7.6 g ; 0.05 mol) and CAB (2.1 g ; 0.01 mol) were made up to 100 ml in 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water, in the presence of 0.5 M perchloric acid. The reaction mixture was kept in the dark for ca 10 hr to ensure completion of the reaction. It was treated overnight with an excess (250 ml) of a freshly prepared saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 M HCl. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, weighed, recrystallised from ethanol, and weighed again. Determination of mixed m.p. and mixed tlc with an authentic sample of DNP confirmed that the product is phenylglyoxylic acid. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallisation were 2.6 g (78%) and 2.3 g (70%) respectively.

Stoichiometry was ascertained by treating mandelic acid (1.52 g ; 0.01 mol) with CAB (10.5 g ; 0.05 mol) in the presence of 0.5 M perchloric acid in 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water. The residual CAB was determined iodometrically. Several determinations with various hydroxy acids indicated a 1 : 1 stoichiometry.

Other experimental details have been described earlier⁸.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for the award of Teacher Fellowship to (A. L. J.) and to Prof. R. C. Kapoor for his keen interest and encouragement.

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